

MATERIALS AND EMOTIONS

A STUDY ON THE RELATIONS BETWEEN MATERIALS AND EMOTIONS IN INDUSTRIAL PRODUCTS

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ABSTRACT

Materials are one of the aspects of a product that have increased in popularity over the last decade. Materials are now considered, not only for their functional role, but also as an inspirational source for designers, who can create new sensorial and expressive experiences and new formal solutions. In the field of design, new research aims to investigate the intangible aspects of materials. This research focuses on the emotional role of materials in user-product interaction. The outcomes include: a set of emotions evoked by materials an evaluation of the capacity of materials to evoke emotions, the role of the emotions evoked by materials and the relationship between emotions and materials in user experience. For a designer it is important to communicate certain emotions and feelings to users. Understanding the relationship between emotions, materials and the user could help designer make choices with different and better awareness.

Keywords: materials, emotions, product experience, material experience, PrEmo

BACKGROUND

Over the last ten years, many researches in the field of design have started to study emotions, in order to develop theories, tools and methods that enable designers to define and quantify the emotions evoked by industrial products.

The emotional relationship between users and products has become a widely explored field of study in a variety of disciplines, and subject areas such as emotional design, product experience and user experience. Thorough research has taken place on a worldwide scale (Schifferstein and Hekkert, 2008; Desmet and Hekkert, 2007; Demirbilek and Sener, 2003; Chitturi, 2009; Kolko, 2011).

Researches in this field focus mainly on classification and schematization of emotions and feelings (Desmet, 2003), on understanding the emotional concepts in users' interaction with products (Demir, 2008; Norman 2004), the appraisal patterns of emotion in human-product interaction (Demir et al., 2009) and the development of tools able to measure the emotional engagement in design field (Desmet, 2003).

Today we know that any design decision can create an emotional effect.

The understanding of user emotions can help the designer to anticipate the emotional impact and therefore to avoid the ones that are unwanted, such as feelings of disgust in response to a new design product (Desmet and Hekkert, 2009).

It is important for a designer to be able to create a product able to evoke a pattern of emotions that the user is expected to experience.

In this research, we investigate the role of materials in products. Materials now, are one of the aspects of a product that has been increased in popularity both in practical and theoretical studies. This has been happened thanks to a number of publications that show the inspirational side of materials.

One of the first publications was *The Material of Invention* by Manzini (1986). This book approaches

materials in a new way that is much closer to the design practice, instead of the traditional idea of materials with only functional and technical properties. The book examines the way in which matter becomes material, i.e. how matter becomes capable of being integrated into design and in the end becomes part of a product through supplying cognitive tools and cultural reference (Manzini, 1986).

Ashby and Johnson (2002) stated that for a designer, “materials are not simply numbers in a data-sheet and design is not a meaningless exercise in styling and it is not an isolated exploration of technology”.

Materials, technologies and finishes are now considered stimuli and inspirational sources for designers who are able to create new sensorial experiences as well as new formal solutions. In this context, the material libraries are growing (Rognoli, 2005) as a source of inspiration and information about materials for design, both in private (e.g. Material Connexion, Materia, etc.) and academic environments (e.g. “Materiali e Design” at Politecnico di Milano, “MatTO” at Politecnico di Torino in Italy, “Made of...” at Delft University in Netherlands, ME-Lab at METU Ankara in Turkey, etc.).

At the same time, new research has started with the aim to investigate different aspects of materials in the design field. The main areas are: research about the expressive-sensorial characterization (Rognoli, 2004; Rognoli and Levi, 2004 a; Zuo et al., 2004; Karana et al., 2009), meanings of materials (Karana, 2009; Karana and Hekkert, 2010), materials selection (Pedgley, 2009, Kesteren 2008), material education (Rognoli, 2010; Pedgley 2010; Rognoli and Levi, 2004 b; Karana, 2011) and sustainability (Rognoli et al. 2011; Ostuzzi et al. 2011).

All of this research considers materials as a physical entity with specific properties but they also recognize them an intangible and undefined value related to their sensorial and expressive properties. These intangible properties affect the selection process through which designers choice of their materials for their products and for this reason it is useful to introduce these themes also in academic education. In addition, the expressive side of materials is increasing their role particularly in the field of aesthetics for sustainability with the aim to affect

engagement between the users and the product (Rognoli et al., 2011).

The emotions evoked by materials can be part of these expressive and intangible properties.

EMOTIONS THROUGH MATERIALS

The literature in the field of design detects form, color and material as fundamental elements of products and strategic aspects in evoking emotions (Ürgen, 2006; Chang and Wu, 2007; Kim and Boradkar, 2002). It has been also stated that the emotional impact of a product depends on its material qualities, purposes, meanings, expressions, and what it does or fails to do (Desmet, 2010).

In this paper, we present the research about the role of materials in user-product interactions and their capability of evoking emotions.

It is known that the materials, from which a product is made, can play a key role in determining how pleasing, or displeasing, a product is for those who experiencing it (Jordan, 2002).

Lefteri (2007) states: “the materials have taken on a role that is not just about basic physical and engineering properties. Materials now perform a role that is in a sense invisible. No longer do we use objects to perform essential functions in our lives: their role are based more on an emotional level”, and materials can contribute.

Materials, indeed, are involved in the emotional process of interaction and they are able to influence the relationship between users and products. (Ashby and Johnson, 2002; Kesteren et al., 2005). Karana (Karana et al., 2008) named the part of product experience that focus on materials, “material experience”. She stated that users describe materials through five categories and one of these categories is the “emotional description” and it is related to the subjective feeling of people towards a material. Karana (2009) also stated that materials are used as the symbols of beliefs: they convey meanings and elicit emotions.

Norman (2004) affirmed that materials of products influence the visceral level of emotions, and they are able to arouse an immediate visceral reaction that he named “wow factor”.

In fact, designers think that the materials and processes are where you can add some spirit to your design and form, visual language, the emotion of the product is always going to be there rather than just the manufacturability, the cost-effectiveness, the production ability (Pedgley, 2009).

Designers have to select materials for their products keeping in mind their emotional capability, with the aim to design a product with an added emotional value also through materials. Truly, designers have the chance to influence the emotional relationship that grows between users and products, indeed, through materials.

The material selection made by designer is different from the process followed by engineers. Designers are not only interested in technical and functional parameters but their choices depend mainly on the sensorial and intangible properties of materials like their personality, the emotions they are able to evoke or the meanings they convey (Ashby and Johnson, 2002; Kesteren, 2008). "The challenge for the designer no longer lies in meeting the functional requirements alone, but in doing so in a way that satisfies the aesthetic and emotional needs" (Ashby and Johnson, 2003).

A robust study was conducted into the emotion of surprise; it has been studied as a design strategy that designers can govern throughout the choice of materials (Ludden et al., 2008).

The above research in its entirety demonstrates that there is a growing interest in the design domain towards the intangible values of materials, i.e., the meanings they evoke or the emotions they elicit (Karana and Hekkert, 2010).

Many researchers have stressed an interest towards an extensive examination of the emotional responses from people and a study, with a focus on emotions elicited by materials that can support designers in defining strategies for developing products that elicit emotions such as curiosity, love, happiness etc. (Karana, 2009).

In order to gather greater knowledge and understanding of the emotional relationship between materials and users, we approach the theme through a study described below.

A STUDY ON HOW EMOTIONS ARE EVOKED BY MATERIAL

The research presented in this paper aims to reveal what aspects of materials evoke emotions and the crucial role they play in evoking emotions in users. In order to achieve our main goal, we set up a study. The aims of the study was to achieve a new understanding of:

- The capacity of materials to evoke emotions;
- The set of emotions evoked by materials;
- The role of emotions evoked by materials;
- The relationship between emotion and materials.

METHOD

The method of the study is described below.

Participants:

The study was conducted with 56 participants (all Italians) divided in 7 different categories of participants. 8 participants (4 male and 4 female) were 20-30 years old non-designers. 8 participants (4 male and 4 female) were 31- 40 years old non-designers, 8 participants (4 male and 4 female) were over 40 non-designers, 8 participants (4 male and 4 female) were students enrolled in a design faculty, 8 participants (4 male and 4 female) were academics and 8 participants (4 male and 4 female) were professionals.

They participated in the study voluntarily.

Stimuli:

The stimulation for the study were 9 different materials (plastic (PP), glass, steel, ceramic, mother of pearl, paper, wood, stone and rubber) embodied in 9 different objects, each of them was made up of one of materials, there were no textures or patterns on them (Figure1).

The objects chosen for conducting the tests were 9 bowls with the same shape and dimension (12 cm diameter and 9 cm height) made of 9 different materials. The bowl was chosen because it is a familiar object, made of one type of material, with a simple shape, concave and convex surfaces, even when you change the materials it maintains the same function, and it was successfully used in a previous study in the meaning of materials (Karana et al.,

2007). At least it was decided to conduct this study with an object, instead of samples, because materials are experienced mainly through the products they are embodied in.

Figure 1 Bowls used in the study. They have approximately the same dimension (12 cm diameter, 9 cm height)

PROCEDURE

Participants were asked to assess the emotions evoked by 9 different materials.

The test was conducted using PrEmo (Desmet, 2003), a tool designed in order to assess emotions evoked by products. PrEmo is a non-verbal self-report instrument designed to understand and evaluate the emotional response to customer products. It measures a set of 12 emotions, 6 positive and 6 negative. Each emotion is portrayed with an animated character and participant express, for each of the 12 emotions, the level of feelings through a scale of 5 intensities (Figure 2).

Each participant individually evaluated the material of the bowls. The products were presented one by one in a random order to each participant. All the bowls were on the table and participants were allowed to hold, watch, touch, and feel the bowl during the evaluation. Participants were asked to focus only on material and avoid, as much as possible, evaluations based on the function of the objects. Each participant took the study in the same condition of light and temperature. The instructions were presented in Italian, verbally, showing a short video tutorial. There were no restrictions of time to report the bowls. The task took approximately 10-12 minutes per participant on average (Figure 3).

RESULTS

All the scores from participants were transferred into data sheet in order to evaluate the relation between each emotion and each material. For all computations, it was calculated a significance level by measuring the mean score. The evaluations with same or higher mean score were selected as a consistent result. Looking at the results it appeared that positive and

Figure 2: PrEmo, the tool used to measure the emotions evoked by materials. In the picture is portrayed the measurement of the emotions evoked by wood. PrEmo was provided by Susagroup with the aim to conduct this research (www.susagroup.com).

Figure 3: Participant who took the test. Participants were asked to evaluate 9 different materials each of them embodied in a bowl. The evaluations was reported through the use of PrEmo, a tool design to measure the emotions evoked by products

negative emotions were experienced with a different level of intensity as a consequence, positive emotions were computed separately from negative emotions (Figure 4). Firstly, the most consistent emotions evoked by materials were calculated. Subsequently

Figure 4. The chart shows the relationship between materials and emotions and the intensity of the emotions felt. The intensity of the emotions is overall low but the chart clearly shows the difference between the positive and the negative emotions felt.

for each consistent emotion, the materials most related were computed.

DISCUSSION

We decided to use the PrEmo instrument for this study because it was designed combining the advantages of both verbal and non-verbal tools, it is able to measure distinct emotions and it can be used to measure mixed emotions (Desmet, 2003). Furthermore, it requires neither expensive equipment nor technical expertise. The value of PrEmo it is also recognized by the intellectual community (Norman, 2002), and it is considered the most significant tool among the tools proposed for the emotional level of product affectation (Demir, 2008).

Although PrEmo is designed to measure emotions in response to product appearance, the tool was used in other contexts, for example in measuring emotions in response to interaction scenarios (e.g. Desmet et al., 2005) and this research shows, that also in the field of materials, interested results were achieved.

The field of materials is different from the field of products, therefore it was expected that the set of emotions experienced toward materials was not the same of the set of the emotions experienced with static products. However, the overall evaluation of products is not apart from the material and they also

play a crucial role. As a consequence, it is expected that some emotions related to products are also connected with materials.

According to the results we can infer:

- The capacity of materials to evoke emotions and the set of emotions evoked by materials.
- As we said before, materials are able to evoked emotions. All the categories of participants considered *disgust* and *fear* emotions less consistent with materials. They explained that they experience rarely these emotions toward materials and they argued that these emotions are mostly evoked by the functionality of the material in relations to the object (for example some participants claimed that rubber is disgusting relating to a bowl if it is used for food, others explained that marble evoked fear because it remind to tombs).
- Desire* is an emotion experienced only towards a specific group of materials (wood, paper, mother of pearl) and it is more linked to products where materials are embodied.
- According to the results of the study, emotions like *pride*, *hope*, *shame*, and *sadness*, referred to materials, are over represented. Most of participants affirmed that it is impossible to experience emotions like shame or sadness through materials, they underlined that these emotions are too strong for this

field. These emotions were linked to materials after longer reflection, and connections were based on complex reflections. Few participants explained that emotions like hope or pride could be evoked by materials only if it is considered the role of this materials in the society (e.g. “Stone evokes me hope because it is a durable material, which has a long life”), or shame was linked to some materials by professionals or academics when they were not able to recognize the families the materials belonged to (“This plastic evokes shame because I am supposed to recognize different types of plastics but actually I did not”).

This study let to know that the emotions most experienced toward materials of product are: *satisfaction, joy, fascination, dissatisfaction and boredom*. These emotions represent a first cross-selection of emotions evoked by materials. It is possible to enlarge this set of emotions through studies conducted previously. Ludden et al. (2008) demonstrated materials are able to evoke surprise, and they identified 6 design strategies to add surprise to products through the correct use of materials. Manzini (1986) also underlined the connections between the emotion of surprise and materials when they cause a visual-touching incongruence, for example in plastic product.

Emotions toward products are part of our daily life, their importance is studied and recognized in many researches (Overbeeke and Hekkert, 1999); McDonagh et al., 2004; Norman 2004), now the experience toward materials is a new field of interest (Karana, 2009; Rognoli, 2004 c) and in this research a first cross-section of emotions experienced interacting with materials has been detected.

- The role of emotions evoked by materials. The aim of this research is also to understand the role of emotion evoked by materials in user experience. Participants, through PrEmo, expressed that materials are able to evoke emotions. However, emotions evoked by materials are weak overall. Based on a scale from 0 to 4 (where 0 means “I do not feel this”, 1 is “I feel this a little”, 2 is “I feel this somewhat”, 3 “I do feel this”, 4 is “I do feel this strongly”) only in few cases participants express they felt the emotions strongly and it happened mostly with a strict

combinations of materials and emotions (wood-satisfaction, paper- fascination, mother of pearl-desire, mother of pearl-satisfaction, mother of pearl-fascination, rubber- fascination, rubber- joy). What’s the role of materials in emotional experience toward products? The results emphasized a strong difference between positive and negative emotions evoked by materials; specifically positive emotions are experienced with higher intensity than negative emotions. That it means product’s material is a factor able to evoke an affective response in human-product interaction.

- The relation between emotion and materials. The study led us to understand that the relationship that exists between materials and emotions. All the participants conveyed that *fascination* is more related to materials like mother of pearl, paper, wood, stone and rubber because the materials are not common uses for a bowl. According to participants, materials able to evoke fascination were rather unusual for the product experienced. Most of participants agreed that *satisfaction* is related mainly to wood, metal and glass but also to mother of pearl. In accordance to them, satisfaction is evoked by functional materials, which enables us to achieve a result and by materials provide sensorial and expressive gratification. *Joy* is evoked mainly by rubber, paper, stone, glass and all materials that maximize or minimize one of their properties. All the participants indicated that ceramic and plastic are the materials mostly associated with boredom, as they are the most common materials for this product. According to them *boredom* is related to repetitiveness through which people experience materials and to lack of new sensorial information. The bowls considered *dissatisfied* are made of plastic, ceramic, paper and rubber. In agreement with them, the dissatisfied materials are materials not capable of reaching efficiently a purpose or materials that not provide sensorial and expressive gratification.

CONCLUSION

Materials are one of the aspects of a product that has been increased in popularity in the last decades. The way to look at materials has changed, materials now are presented as an inspirational source for designer, and no there is a growing interest in the

design domain towards the intangible values of materials. Designers have become conscious that materials are able to give rise to emotions and feelings and they arouse an immediate visceral reaction.

There are many strategies through which designers can design products with an added emotional value, (Desmet, 2002; Ludden, 2008) a more aware choice of materials, is one these.

This research shows that materials play an important role in the evaluation of products and they are able to evoke emotions in user-product interactions. There are some emotions than can be evoked mainly by whole product, others that are more related to material. A first set of emotions, positive and negative, evoked by materials found: *satisfaction, joy, fascination, surprise, dissatisfaction and boredom*. Although the intensity of the emotion through which the material are experienced is not high, materials play a crucial role in the overall evaluations of products and they can increase or decrease the product experience. The intensity through which positive emotions are experienced towards materials is higher than the intensity of negative emotions. This means that materials are strength, and they can improve the overall experience. Designers through the choice of the material can completely change the experience towards products and actually, they can design products with an added emotional value using materials. It is important to underline that design products with an added emotional value could have relevant implications.

The affective response arouses through the involvement with products can have significant implications. For example, the emotional relationship between the user and the product can affect the product lifetime. Related to this theme there are some interesting facts founded in research (Mugge et al., 2009, Schifferstein, and Zwartkruis-Pelgrim, 2008). And we can suppose that materials can be also involved.

FUTURE DEVELOPMENTS

It is stated that the emotional experience and journey is part of product experience (Desmet and Hekkert, 2007) and it is described as an experience that pulls us towards products that are, or promise to be,

beneficial or push us from those that are detrimental for our well being (Desmet et al. 2001).

The emotional experience with products is connected with the experience of meaning and the aesthetic experience. The aesthetic experience involves a product's capacity to delight on or more sensorial modalities, and it is strictly likened to materials, as they are mainly experience through senses. In literature, sensorial properties of materials are recognized as one of the most influential aspects of materials in determining the affective responses of user. (Fenech and Borg, 2006; Rognoli and Levi, 2004; Karana et al., 2009; Zuo et al., 2005 Sonneveld, 2007;). Mc Donald and Rashid also stated that sensory aspects of product design in user-product interaction create an experience. (MacDonald 2001; Rashid, 2003).

The future development of this research will be new studies designed with the aim of achieving and understanding of the relation between emotions evoked by materials and sensorial properties.

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